

Title	#	ISBN	Description	Author/Editor (FN, LN)	Publication Year	Author/Editor (LN, FN)	Publisher	Place
"Get That Nigger Off The Field": A Sparkling, Informal History Of The Black Man In Baseball		9780440027911	Arthur George Rust Jr. was a successful sports broadcaster for half a century. He was also a sports historian and author. His controversially-titled first book explores the rocky beginnings of blacks in baseball.	Art Rust	1976	Rust, Art	Delacorte Press	
"If You Were Only White": The Life Of Leroy "Satchel" Paige		9780826272805	If You Were Only White explores the legacy of one of the most exceptional athletes ever—an entertainer extraordinaire, a daring showman and crowd-pleaser, a wizard with a baseball whose artistry and antics on the mound brought fans out in the thousands to ballparks across the country. Leroy "Satchel" Paige was arguably one of the world's greatest pitchers and a premier star of Negro Leagues Baseball. But in this biography, Donald Spivey reveals Paige to have been much more than just a blazing fastball pitcher. Spivey follows Paige from his birth in Alabama in 1906 to his death in Kansas City in 1982, detailing the challenges Paige faced battling the color line in America and recounting his tests and triumphs in baseball. He also opens up Paige's private life during and after his playing days, introducing listeners to the man who extended his social, cultural, and political reach beyond the limitations associated with his humble background.	Donald Spivey	2012	Spivey, Donald	University of Missouri Press	Columbia, MO
A Game For All Races		9781567994193	Paige's life intertwined with many of the most important issues of the times in US and African American history. Spivey incorporates interviews with former teammates conducted over twelve years, as well as exclusive interviews with Paige's son Robert, daughter Pamela, Ted "Double Duty" Radcliffe, and John "Buck" O'Neil to tell the story of a pioneer who helped transform America through the nation's favorite pastime.	Henry Metcalfe	2000	Metcalfe, Henry	MetroBooks	New York, NY
A Negro League Scrapbook		9781590780916	A history of Negro League baseball presents an array of historical photographs and artwork, biographical sketches of Negro League stars and their accomplishments, and a study of the league and its social, cultural, and political significance	Carole Boston Weatherford & Buck O'Neil	2005	Weatherford, Carole Boston; O'Neil, Buck	Boyd's Mills Press	Honesdale, PA
A Strong Right Arm: The Story Of Mamie "Peanut" Johnson		9780142400722	New York Times best-selling author Carole Boston Weatherford compiles an enthralling summary of Negro League history that includes fascinating tidbits about prominent pitchers, hitters, utility players, teams, and traditions. Motivated by her love for the game and inspired by the legendary Jackie Robinson, Mamie Johnson is determined to be a professional baseball pitcher. But in a sport that's determined by white men, there is no place for a black woman. Mamie doesn't give up—from the time she insists on trying out for the all-male, all-white Police Athletic League until she realizes her dream and becomes one of three women to play in the Negro Leagues. Mamie Johnson's life shows that with courage and perseverance one can overcome even the greatest challenges.	Michelle Y Green & Mamie Johnson	2004	Green, Michelle Y.; Johnson, Mamie	Puffin Books	
Amazing Baseball Heroes: Inspirational Negro League Stories		9781932604818	Amazing Baseball Heroes profiles twenty American baseball legends—including Jackie Robinson—complete with statistics and facts that show their athletic skills and determination were second to none. They overcame the lack of educational opportunities, poverty, and racial discrimination, yet they refused to give in and were not outplayed.	Bryan Stevenson	2011	Stevenson, Bryan	Tennessee Valley Publishing	Knoxville, TN
Art Rust's Illustrated History Of The Black Athlete		9780385151399	Offers brief profiles of top Black athletes in baseball, boxing, basketball, football, track, golf, ice hockey, tennis, and horse racing and reviews the history of each sport	Edna Rust & Art Rust	1985	Rust, Edna; Rust, Art; Rust, Edna	Doubleday	Garden City, NY
Baseball Has Done It		9780975215720	Back in print for the first time since its initial publication in 1964, Baseball Has Done It is an oral history of baseball and racial integration as told by its greatest players to the man who broke the color line, Jackie Robinson. This one-of-a-kind classic features rare and candid interviews conducted by Robinson with ballplayers who played and lived through the first generation of racial integration in baseball. A who's who of baseball legends—Hank Aaron, Ernie Banks, Roy Campanella, Alvin Dark, Larry Doby, Carl Erskine, Elston Howard, Monte Irvin, Don Newcombe, Frank Robinson and Bill White—share the spotlight with players from the Negro Leagues, baseball executives like Branch Rickey and Ford Frick and Jackie Robinson himself to create a diverse look at the effects of integration on baseball and society.	Jackie Robinson	2005	Robinson, Jackie	Ig Publishing	St. Paul, MN
Baseball's Great Experiment: Jackie Robinson And His Legacy		9780195339284	In this gripping account of one of the most important steps in the history of American desegregation, Jules Tygiel tells the story of Jackie Robinson's crossing of baseball's color line. Examining the social and historical context of Robinson's introduction into white organized baseball, both on and off the field, Tygiel also tells the often neglected stories of other African-American players—such as Satchel Paige, Roy Campanella, Willie Mays, and Hank Aaron—who helped transform our national pastime into an integrated game. Drawing on dozens of interviews with players and front office executives, contemporary newspaper accounts, and personal papers, Tygiel provides the most telling and insightful account of Jackie Robinson's influence on American baseball and society. The anniversary issue features a new foreword by the author.	Jules Tygiel	2008	Tygiel, Jules	Oxford University Press	
Black Ball II: The Negro Baseball Leagues, A Book Of Postcards			Discover the rich history of African American baseball with "Black Ball: The Negro Baseball Leagues Postcards" book. This collection features two autographs from Ernie Westfield, making it a unique addition to any sports memorabilia collection. The book contains 30 pages of stunning illustrations and informative text, providing a glimpse into the world of Negro League baseball.		2004		Pomegranate Artbooks	San Francisco, CA
Black Ball: A Negro Leagues Journal			Under the guidance of Leslie Heaphy and an editorial board of leading historians, this peer-reviewed, annual book series offers new, authoritative research on all subjects related to black baseball, including the Negro major and minor leagues, teams, and players; pre-Negro League organization and play; barnstorming; segregation and integration; class, gender, and ethnicity; the business of black baseball; and the arts.	Leslie Heaphy	2008		McFarland & Company	
Black Ball: The Negro Baseball Leagues, A Book Of Postcards.		9780876549438	Discover the rich history of African American baseball with "Black Ball: The Negro Baseball Leagues Postcards" book. This collection features two autographs from Ernie Westfield, making it a unique addition to any sports memorabilia collection. The book contains 30 pages of stunning illustrations and informative text, providing a glimpse into the world of Negro League baseball.		1991		Pomegranate Artbooks	San Francisco, CA
Black Barons Of Birmingham: The South's Greatest Negro League Team And Its Players		9780786454808	A unique approach to the history of a Negro League team: The first half of this book covers the leagues and the players of the 1920s, the 1930s, and 1940 through 1947 (when Robinson broke the color barrier). The second half is devoted to the Black Barons of subsequent decades—the former Barons invited to tryout camps, others who were signed with minor league clubs, and the fortunate few who got their long-awaited chance in the majors.	Larry Powell	2009	Powell, Larry	McFarland & Company	Jefferson, NY
Blackball Stars: Negro League Pioneers		9780887360947	Looks at the history of the Black major leagues, offers profiles of some of the top players, and describes the contributions of Black professional baseball	John Holway	1988	Holway, John	Meckler Books	Westport, CT
Bud Fowler: Baseball's First Black Professional		9781476603773	This is the biography of Bud Fowler (ne John Jackson), the first African American to play in organized baseball, and the longest tenured at the time that the color line was drawn. In addition to his professional playing career, which lasted more than 25 years, Fowler was a scout, organizer, owner, and promoter of touring black baseball clubs—including the legendary Paige Fence Giants—in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.	Jeffrey Michael Laing	2013	Laing, Jeffrey Michael	McFarland & Company	Jefferson, NY

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Crossing The Line: Black Major Leaguers, 1947-1959		9780899509303	On April 15, 1947, Jackie Robinson opened the season at first base for the Brooklyn Dodgers, going 0 for 3 with a sacrifice and integrating major league baseball. Though stars such as Willie Mays and Hank Aaron quickly made their marks, it was not until 1959 that the Boston Red Sox called up a light-hitting infielder named Pumpsie Green, thus to become the last team to break baseball's color barrier. From 1947 through 1959, over 100 African American players made it to the major leagues. Each of these players is profiled in this comprehensive reference work that profiles their playing careers and the on- and off-field difficulties they encountered in integrating the game. Some were stars, most (such as Green, Billy Bruton, and Harry Simpson) were average players, but all were pioneers in the sport. For each, career statistics and a capsule biography are provided.	Larry Moffi & Jonathan Kronstadt	1994	Moffi, Larry; Kronstadt, Jonathan	McFarland & Company	Jefferson, NC
Few And Chosen: Defining Negro Leagues Greatness		9781572438552	Monte Irvin, a New York Giants star player who got his start in the Negro Leagues, pays homage to baseball's finest heroes and long-forgotten stars by selecting the top five players at each position and the top five managers, owners, pioneers, or organizers from the Negro Leagues.	Monte Irvin & Phil Pepe	2007	Irvin, Monte; Pepe, Phil	Triumph Books	Chicago, IL
Fleet Walker's Divided Heart: The Life Of Baseball's First Black Major Leaguer		9780803249134	A gifted athlete, inventor, civil rights activist, author, and entrepreneur, Walker lived precariously along America's racial fault lines. He died in 1924, thwarted in ambition and talent and frustrated by both the American dream and the national pastime.	David Zang	1995	Zang, David	University of Nebraska Press	
Heroes Of The Negro Leagues		9780810994348	First published as trading cards in 1990, these out-of-print watercolor images by award-winning artist Mark Chiarello are now collected for the first time in book form, along with incisive text by Jack Morelli and 39 brand-new images created especially for this book, including portraits of Satchel Paige, Hank Aaron, and Jackie Robinson. The legendary Negro Leagues are regarded with reverence and awe, and play a vital role in black history. The publication of these cards marked the first time most of these players ever appeared on baseball cards.	Jack Morelli & Mark Chiarello	2007	Morelli, Jack; Chiarello, Mark	Abrams	
Innings Ago: Recollections By Kansas City Ballplayers Of Their Days In The Game		9780916399481	An Oral history of baseball in Kansas City, Missouri	Jack Etkin	1987	Etkin, Jack	Normandy Square Publications	Kansas City, MO
Invisible Men: Life In Baseball's Negro Leagues		9780689113635	This remarkable narrative is filled with the memories of many surviving Negro League players. What emerges is a glorious chapter in African American history and an often overlooked aspect of our American past.	Donn Rogosin	1983	Rogosin, Donn	Atheneum	
Jackie Robinson: An Intimate Portrait		9780810981898	In an evocative and personal memoir enhanced by hundreds of photographs, the widow of Jackie Robinson provides an intimate portrait of her husband, his rise to success, the impact of his fame on the family, and his life after baseball.	Rachel Robinson & Lee Daniels	1998	Robinson, Rachel; Daniels, Lee	Harry N. Abrams	London, England
Jackie Robinson: The Faith Of A Boundary-Breaking Hero		9780664262037	Jackie Robinson believed in a God who sides with the oppressed and who calls us to see one another as sisters and brothers. This faith was a powerful but quiet engine that drove and sustained him as he shattered racial barriers on and beyond the baseball diamond. Jackie Robinson: A Spiritual Biography explores the faith that, Robinson said, carried him through the torment and abuse he suffered for integrating the major leagues and drove him to get involved in the civil rights movement. Marked by sacrifice and service, inclusiveness and hope, Robinson's faith shaped not only his character but also baseball and America itself.	Michael G. Long & Chris Lamb	2017	Long, Michael G.; Lamb, Chris	Presbyterian Publishing Corporation	Louisville, KY
Josh Gibson: A Life In The Negro Leagues		9780060104467	An account of the life, flamboyant and legendary career, and final downhill years of the man who was called the black Babe Ruth and who died, at thirty-five, during the winter after Jackie Robinson broke the minor league's color barrier.	William Brashler	1978	Brashler, William	Harper & Row	
Just Let Me Play: The Story Of Charlie Sifford, The First Black PGA Golfer		9780945167440	The first black golfer on the PGA tells of the consistent battles he has waged against bigotry in the exclusive world of golf and tells how his courage has opened the sport to a new generation of blacks.	Charlie Sifford & Jim Gullo	1992	Sifford, Charlie; Gullo, Jim	British American Pub	Latham, NY
Only The Ball Was White: A History Of Legendary Black Players And All-black Professional Teams		9780195076370	In Only the Ball Was White, Robert Peterson tells the forgotten story of these excluded ballplayers, and gives them the recognition they were so long denied. Reconstructing the old Negro Leagues from contemporary sports publications, accounts of games in the black press, and through interviews with the men who actually played the game, Peterson brings to life the fascinating period that stretched from shortly after the Civil War to the signing of Jackie Robinson in 1947. We watch as the New York Black Yankees and the Philadelphia Crawfords take the field, look on as the East-West All-Star lineups are announced, and listen as the players themselves tell of the struggle and glory that was black baseball. In addition to these vivid accounts, Peterson includes yearly Negro League standings and an all-time register of players and officials, making the book a treasure trove of baseball information and lore.	Robert Peterson	1992	Peterson, Robert	Oxford University Press	
Our Team: The Epic Story Of Four Men And The World Series That Changed Baseball		9781250266316	In intimate, absorbing detail, Luke Epplin's Our Team traces the story of the integration of the Cleveland Indians and their quest for a World Series title through four key participants: Bill Veeck, an eccentric and visionary owner adept at exploding fireworks on and off the field; Larry Doby, a soft-spoken, hard-hitting pioneer whose major-league breakthrough shattered stereotypes that so much of white America held about Black ballplayers; Bob Feller, a pitching prodigy from the Iowa cornfields who set the template for the athlete as businessman; and Satchel Paige, a legendary pitcher from the Negro Leagues whose belated entry into the majors whipped baseball fans across the country into a frenzy. Together, as the backbone of a team that epitomized the postwar American spirit in all its hopes and contradictions, these four men would captivate the nation by storming to the World Series—all the while rewriting the rules of what was possible in sports.	Luke Epplin	2022	Epplin, Luke	Flatiron Books	
Playing America's Game: Baseball, Latinos, And The Color Line		9780520236462	Although largely ignored by historians of both baseball in general and the Negro leagues in particular, Latinos have been a significant presence in organized baseball from the beginning. In this benchmark study on Latinos and professional baseball from the 1980s to the present, Adrian Burgos tells a compelling story of the men who negotiated the color line at every turn—passing as “Spanish” in the major leagues or seeking respect and acceptance in the Negro leagues.	Adrian Burgos	2007	Burgos, Adrian	University of California Press	
Pride Against Prejudice: The Biography Of Larry Doby		9780313259951	As the second black major league baseball player, following Jackie Robinson, Larry Doby has never received the acclaim accorded to Robinson; yet his experiences of segregation and racial invective, and his courage and ability to excel in the face of almost overwhelming circumstances, were equivalent. This fascinating biography brings to light interesting and little-known facts concerning Doby's life and baseball career, and his contribution as a civil rights pioneer in the American League. His story is perceived as the story of the many black men who followed him into major league baseball, and who shared importantly in pioneering the integration of the sport.	Joseph Moore	1988	Moore, Joseph	Praeger	
Satchel Sez: The Wit, Wisdom, And World Of Leroy "Satchel" Paige		9780609806432	Satchel Paige's witty quips and savvy observations – on everything from health to wealth, from race relations to baseball – are an enduring part of American mythology. At long last, a definitive collection of quotes, stories (from Willie Mays, Joe DiMaggio, and others), vintage newspaper articles, photos, and memorabilia celebrates the inimitable magic of Leroy "Satchel" Paige.	Satchel Paige, David Sterry & Arielle Eckstut	2001	Paige, Satchel; Sterry, David; Eckstut, Arielle	Three Rivers Press	New York, NY
Satchel: The Life And Times Of An American Legend		9780812977974	Few reliable records or news reports survive about players in the Negro Leagues. Through dogged detective work, award-winning author and journalist Larry Tye has tracked down the truth about this majestic and enigmatic pitcher, interviewing more than two hundred Negro Leagues and Major Leaguers, talking to family and friends who had never told their stories before, and retracing Paige's steps across the continent.	Larry Tye	2010	Tye, Larry	Random House	New York, NY

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Shades Of Glory: The Negro Leagues And The Story Of African-American Baseball		9780792253068	Celebrating African America's contribution to our great national pastime, this comprehensive, lively history combines vivid narrative, visual impact, and a unique statistical component, to recreate the excitement and passion of the Negro Leagues. Packed with stories, biographical essays, scores of archival photographs and other evocative artifacts, it is an important contribution to sports history and a wonderful tribute to the players and teams who wrote a unique chapter in the annals of baseball and American culture.	Lawrence Hogan & National Baseball Hall of Fame and Museum	2006	Hogan, Lawrence D.; National Baseball Hall of Fame and Museum	National Geographic Society	Washington, DC
Smoke: The Romance And Lore Of Cuban Baseball		9781892129321	Exploring the history and variety of Cuban baseball, a unique exploration of this "last frontier" of American sport uses photographic, statistics, and baseball lore to trace the sport's history, from its origins in the 1970s to the current American love affair with their version of the game. 25,000 first printing.	Mark Rucker & Peter C. Bjarkman	1999	Rucker, Mark; Bjarkman, Peter C.	Total Sports Illustrated	
Some Are Called Clowns: A Season With The Last Of The Great Barnstorming Baseball Teams		9780690004694	Some are called clown tells the sometime outrageously funny, sometimes tragic story of a unique American phenomenon, the barnstorming baseball team. Every player is reminded rightly that he is "trying to follow in the footsteps of the great Hank Aaron who started his career with the Indianapolis Clowns," whether PA blares the introductions. To the other clowns, the contortionists, the midgets, the one armed first baseman, and acrobats, it's a performance and, no matter what the size of the gate, the show must go on.	Bill Heward & Dimitri V. Gat	1974	Heward, Bill; Gat, Dimitri V.	Crowell	
The Integration Of Major League Baseball: A Team By Team History		9780786453344	This book is a record of the men and events, team by team, during Major League Baseball's integration. It focuses especially on the owners, executives and managers who were the heroes, villains or spectators of integration, and it sheds new light on the unheralded champions of integration and on those whose culpability has so far been overlooked. Individual chapters cover each of baseball's integration-era teams, and a final chapter covers expansion teams of the 1960s. Each team's responsible individuals are examined, its acquisition, deployment and treatment of black players documented, and the effect of its integration actions on team performance analyzed. Appendices provide populations of integration-era Major League cities, first black players by team, first black players in various minor leagues, rosters of black players by team, a timeline of black player milestones, and a list of black All-Star selections through 1969.	Rick Swaine	2009	Swaine, Rick	McFarland & Company	Jefferson, NY
The Integration Of The Pacific Coast League: Race And Baseball On The West Coast		9781496207081	The Integration of the Pacific Coast League describes the evolution of the PCL beginning with the league's differing treatment of African Americans and other nonwhite players. Between the 1900s and the 1930s, team owners knowingly signed Hawaiian players, Asian players, and African American players who claimed that they were Native Americans, who were not officially banned. In the post-World War II era, with the pressures and challenges facing desegregation, the league gradually accepted African American players. In the 1940s individual players and the local press challenged the segregation of the league. Because these Minor League teams integrated so much earlier than the Major Leagues or the eastern Minor Leagues, West Coast baseball fans were the first to experience a more diverse baseball game.	Amy Essington	2018	Essington, Amy	University of Nebraska Press	
The Kansas City Monarchs: Champions Of Black Baseball		978070602735	Charter members of the Negro National League, stepping stone for Jackie Robinson, home base for Satchel Paige, and training ground for more than twenty blacks sent to the major leagues, the Kansas City Monarchs survived the entire thirty-five-year span of black baseball (from 1920 to mid 1950) and were widely regarded as the dominant black professional team, "the New York Yankees of the Negro leagues." Rich in anecdote and illustrated with more than ninety photographs of Monarchs players and scenes, this book is both a tribute to and a celebration of the top all-black team of all time.	Janet Bruce	1985	Bruce, Janet	University Press of Kansas	Lawrence, KS
The Negro Leagues Are Major Leagues: Essays And Research For Overdue Recognition		9781970159639	The Negro Leagues are Major Leagues is a unique introduction to the history of the segregation of professional baseball, telling the story of the Negro Leagues while simultaneously recounting how researchers, statisticians, and historians rebuilt and rediscovered the history of Black baseball that was pushed into obscurity in the wake of Jackie Robinson and integration.	Sean Forman & Cecilia M. Tan	2021	Forman, Sean; Tan, Cecilia M.	Society for American Baseball Research (SABR)	Phoenix, AZ
The Soul Of Baseball: A Road Trip Through Buck O'Neil's America		9780060854041	The Soul of Baseball is as much the story of Buck O'Neil as it is the story of baseball. Driven by a relentless optimism and his two great passions - for America's pastime and for jazz, America's music - O'Neil played solely for love. In an era when greedy, steroid-enhanced athletes have come to characterize professional ball, Posnanski offers a salve for the damaged spirit: the uplifting life lessons of a truly extraordinary man who never missed an opportunity to enjoy and love life.	Joe Posnanski	2008	Posnanski, Joe	HarperCollins Publishers	New York, NY
When The Game Was Black And White: The Illustrated History Of The Negro Leagues		9781558593725	Traces the history of the Negro baseball leagues, offers profiles of top players and their accomplishments, and shares the memories of players and fans.	Bruce Chadwick	1992	Chadwick, Bruce	Abbeville Press	New York, NY
Wilber "Bullet" Rogan And The Kansas City Monarchs		9780786444250	Both a biography of Wilber "Bullet" Rogan and a history of his great Kansas City Monarchs teams, 1920-1938, this detailed work pays tribute to a man considered by some to be baseball's greatest all-around player. During his career, the Monarchs won two Negro League World Series and five pennants, in addition to launching the careers of several outstanding players and conducting many barnstorming tours. The author, who interviewed many former players, covers Rogan's Hall of Fame career in-depth and brings to light one of baseball's greatest but often forgotten talents.	Phil Dixon	2010	Dixon, Phil	McFarland & Company	Jefferson, NC